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RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>GaN HEMT Reliability in Atmospheric Environment</i>
Project TA identifier	<i>TA08-233</i>
General application	<i>Research</i>
Type of test	<i>SEE, Long term reliability analysis</i>
Group leader, Institute	<i>Kimmo Niskanen, JYU</i>
Date(s) of the experiment	<i>March 15 - 17, 2024</i>
Facility	<i>Chiplr</i>
Amount of access granted (unit of access: 1h)	<i>24</i>

Objectives of the experiments

This work focused on the impact of atmospheric neutrons on long term reliability of the COTS GaN - based power HEMTs and SiC-based power MOSFETs, especially focusing on gate reliability degradation due to non-destructive radiation effects. Long term reliability degradation is studied by applying post-irradiation electrical stress on the devices. The effect of bias conditions and neutron fluence on the degradation and latent damage is studied.

Currently, the radiation test methods for power electronic devices that have been developed for Si-based technologies fail to take into account the possible latent damage and its impact on the device long term reliability. Post-irradiation gate stress (PIGS) is mentioned in MIL-STD-750E method 1080 (SEE test method), but it only covers the rated voltage region and does not consider the possible lifetime reduction which can be revealed through accelerated TDDB and gate breakdown tests. Therefore, this work on its part can help to develop more dedicated test methods for lifetime estimation of emerging power devices in radiation environments.

Experiment test report

The devices under test (DUT) are discrete commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) gallium nitride (GaN) power HEMTs (EPC2012C) and silicon carbide (SiC)-based power MOSFETs (C3M0350120D) and diodes (C6D08065A and C6D04065A). The DUTs were connected in parallel on the test board and one SMU was used to apply the voltage and measure the current at the board level during the irradiation runs. The whole DUT area of the test board was exposed to the beam at normal incidence. Voltages and currents of the test board were monitored during the beam exposure.

The irradiation part of this experiment was conducted successfully. The main goal of the experiment is in the long term reliability analysis, which takes several months to finish. Therefore, there are no data to show at this point. Detailed results will be disseminated in a conference and/or journal paper.

<https://radnext.web.cern.ch/>

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After the beam exposure, devices are exposed to long duration electrical stresses in order to reveal possible latent damage induced reliability degradation. The method which is used to reveal such degradation is developed by using the irradiated samples. The irradiation was performed in such voltage conditions where no or very few device failures such as single event burnout (SEB) or single event gate rupture (SEGR) were observed.

Irradiation runs are summarized in the table below. All irradiations were performed with $V_{GS}=0V$ and the neutron flux was $5e6 \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$

<i>DUT</i>	<i>V_{DS}</i> (V)	<i>V_{GS}</i> (V)	<i>Fluence (cm-2)</i>	<i>Failures/Total DUTs</i>
C3M0350120D	1000	0	1.14E+10	13/14
	1000	0	1.19E+10	10/14
	1000	0	1.83E+10	10/10
	1000	0	1.47E+10	14/14
	900	0	1.72E+10	3/10
	900	0	1.00E+10	4/10
	800	0	1.02E+10	1/10
	700	0	1.02E+10	0/10
	700	0	1.04E+10	0/10
	700	0	1.00E+10	0/10
	700	0	1.00E+10	0/10
	700	0	1.01E+10	1/10
	600	0	9.97E+09	0/10
	0	20	1.02E+10	0/10
C6D08065A	0	-10	1.01E+10	0/10
	600	N/A	1.70E+09	9/9
	300	N/A	1.61E+11	0/9
C6D04065A	0	N/A	1.61E+11	0/9
	550	N/A	7.10E+09	9/9
	350	N/A	3.15E+10	0/9
EPC2012C	200	0	1.00E+10	0/10
	200	-3	1.01E+10	0/10
	200	0	1.01E+09	0/10

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	
Follow-up experiment at same facility	X
Follow-up experiment at another facility	X
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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